

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Titanium Present in Rocks and Minerals

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Titanium (IV) forms an orange yellow coloured chelate with salicylhydroxamic acid at pH 1.5-2.0 having the composition $TiO(C_7H_5O_3N)_2$ in the solid state, is extractable with isoamyl alcohol and the colour of the extract can be directly measured spectrophotometrically at 348 nm. The system follows Beer's law at 348 nm over the concentration range 0.1 ppm to 10.0 ppm of titanium, with a sensitivity of $0.0083 \mu g Ti cm^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity of 5769. The method is found suitable for determination of titanium present in the silicate rocks and minerals for which this has been successfully employed.

TITANIUM(IV) forms orange yellow chelate compounds with different hydroxamic acids¹⁻⁹, of which the one obtained with salicylhydroxamic acid has been found to be easily extractable in isoamyl alcohol in acid medium giving rise to an intense yellow solution. On the basis of this a rapid sensitive method for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of the metal has been formulated. The composition of the solid product isolated has been established as $TiO(C_7H_5O_3N)_2$ for which IR studies have been made. The method has been utilised for the determination of trace amounts of Ti present in silicate rocks and minerals

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents

A Beckman D.B. automatic recording spectrophotometer was used for the absorbance measurements and all pH measurements were made with a Beckman pH-meter.

The reagent salicylhydroxamic acid was used after crystallization of the ordinary product for several times, (m.p. 167°-168°). All the reagents including isoamyl alcohol were of analytical grade. Buffer solutions were prepared in the usual way¹⁰.

Stock solutions of titanium were prepared from potassium titanyl fluoride (AR) and the titanium contents estimated by the cupferron method¹¹. A 0.01M salicylhydroxamic acid was prepared in isoamyl alcohol (0.153%). Solutions of other diverse ions were prepared by dissolving analytical grade reagents.

Absorbance curves

The absorbances of the orange yellow titanium(IV)-salicylhydroxamic acid extract in isoamyl alcohol at pH 1.5 to 2.0 shows the maximum absorption at the

wavelength 348 nm. The absorbance curve shows a peak at 348 nm (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. I. Absorption Spectrum of Ti(IV)—Salicylhydroxamic Acid Chelate Extracted in Isoamyl alcohol at pH 1.5 Vs Reagent Blank (Ti(IV)=5.0 ppm). II. Absorption Spectrum of Reagent Blank at pH 1.5.

Effect of pH

Complete extraction of titanium(IV)-salicylhydroxamic acid chelate was found to be possible between pH 1.5 to 2.0 in which range all the extractions were carried out. The percentage extraction of titanium (IV)-salicylhydroxamic acid chelate at different pH-values were calculated as shown in Fig. 2.

Reagent Concentration

Isoamyl alcohol containing 0.01M of salicylhydroxamic acid was found to be most suitable for

extraction of titanium. With lower the reagent concentration insufficient extraction of titanium resulted which were remedied by further extractions.

Fig. 2. I. Extraction of Ti(IV)—Salicylhydroxamate Chelate as a function of pH (Ti(IV)=5.0 ppm).
 II. Absorbance of Ti(IV)—Salicylhydroxamate complex extract as a function of pH (Ti(IV)=5.0 ppm)

Beer's law and standard curves

The extracted chelate solution was found to obey Beer's law at 348 nm over the concentration range of 0.10 ppm to 10 ppm of titanium. The sensitivities $\log I_0/I = 0.001$, calculated as described by Sandell, is $0.0083 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for titanium with a molar absorptivity of 5769.

Period of extraction

An extraction period 5 minutes was found to be optimum and the resulting orange yellow coloured extract in isoamyl alcohol has been found to remain stable for a few days.

Effect of diverse ions

In the presence of ions listed below, 5 ppm of titanium could be determined after extraction with salicylhydroxamic acid in isoamyl alcohol from pH 1.5-2.0 without interference. Al^{+3} (100 ppm), Cu^{+2} (100 ppm), Co^{+2} (100 ppm), Cd^{+2} (100 ppm), Hg^{+2} (100 ppm), Pb^{+2} (100 ppm), Be^{+2} (100 ppm), Ni^{+2} (100 ppm), Zn^{+2} (100 ppm), Sn^{+2} (50 ppm), UO_2 (50 ppm), Cr^{+3} (50 ppm), Pd^{+2} (20 ppm), V^{+5} (10 ppm), Mo^{+6} (20 ppm), fluoride (20 ppm), oxalate (20 ppm), tartarate (20 ppm), phosphate (50 ppm), citrate (20 ppm), and borate (20 ppm) and also in presence of large amount of alkali and alkaline earth metals. The interference due to Fe^{+3} can be masked with thioglycolic acid.

Composition

Ti(IV) forms an orange yellow compound with salicylhydroxamic acid at pH 1.0 to 2.0 which on analysis corresponds to the formula $\text{TiO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{N})_2$ where metal reagent ratio is 1:2.^{3,4} In the IR spectra analysis the stretching frequency observed at 3250 cm^{-1} , 1600 cm^{-1} , 920 cm^{-1} , correspond to $\nu\text{O-H}$, $\nu\text{C=O}$, and $\nu\text{N-O}$. It has been observed

that the absorption bands due to (O-H) stretching vibrations when free appear around 3325 cm^{-1} , free (C=O) stretching vibrations around 1620 cm^{-1} and free (N-O) stretching vibrations at 910 cm^{-1} .¹¹ The IR spectra of $\text{TiO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{N})_2$ in KBr pallet has a band of medium intensity at 865 cm^{-1} , may correspond due to M=O bonds¹⁰. The orange yellow chelate having possible species (MOR_2) is extractable with isoamyl alcohol.

General Procedure

10 ml. of titanium solution containing 50 ppm of titanium and 9 ml. of KCl-HCl buffer of pH 1.0 were taken in a 50 ml. separatory funnel. After adding 10 ml. of 0.01M salicylhydroxamic acid solution in isoamyl alcohol, the mixture was shaken for 5 min and allowed to stand, till the organic and the aqueous phases were separated. The aqueous phase was collected separately and pH of the solution was determined. Organic phase was collected and the clear solution after treatment with anhydrous sodium sulphate was taken in a 10 ml. volumetric flask and made upto the required volume with 0.01M salicylhydroxamic acid in isoamyl alcohol. The absorbance was measured at 348 nm against the reagent blank.

*Determination of Titanium in the silicate rocks and minerals*¹²⁻¹⁵

The constituents of the rocks are mainly, aluminium, manganese, iron, copper, titanium, vanadium, calcium, magnesium etc. Powdered rock (1 g) was fused after mixing with 5 g of anhydrous sodium carbonate in a platinum crucible in the usual manner. The melt is leached with dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered. To the filtrate 10% caustic soda solution was added, till the precipitation was completed. After filtration the residue was freed from alkali and dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and collected in a 50 ml volumetric flask. The titanium present in the silicate rocks was determined in the usual way after adding 5% thioglycolic acid.

Titanium found in the rock sample

Rock sample	Titanium (by given method) in ppm.	Titanium (by standard method) in ppm.
S ₁	440	431
S ₂	510	502
S ₃	690	695
S ₄	850	843

Titanium in illeminite

It has been seen that titanium in illeminite is easily determined after treating the ore about (0.1 g) with HF, H_2SO_4 and a few drops of HNO_3 and evaporated to remove all fluoride. The solution was taken in dilute H_2SO_4 and filtered into a 250 ml measuring flask. The titanium present in the stock solution was determined following the procedure

developed using thioglycolic acid as the masking agent.

	Ti % (by std method)	Amount of the sample	Ti% (by given method)
(1) Illemenite	31.40	0.1150	31.46
		0.1025	31.44
(2) Illemenite	30.53	0.1095	30.61
		0.1125	30.57

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